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Executive Summary

This document has reported about the technical progress during the first year of the AMADEUS project. It contains a summary of the key developments on the energy storage module (WP2), the energy conversion module (WP3) and the first steps towards the achievement of the final proof of concept experiment (WP4).

Concerning the energy storage block (WP2), it has been theoretically predicted that the eutectic Si-3B (wt%) alloy has a larger latent heat and lower melting point than pure silicon. DSC, LFA and TG techniques have been used to experimentally determine the thermophysical properties of Si-B alloys and refractories (BN, C, SiC, ZrO₂ and Si₃N₄). Special attention has been paid to the DSC characterization of Si and Si-B alloys in the liquid state. The high reactivity with conventional crucible materials used in DSC devices has required the development of a new setup able to reach temperatures above 1500°C. DSC measurements of Si-B alloys are being currently carried out in this new setup. Also, the interaction of Si and Si-B alloys with refractories up to temperatures of ~1750°C has been explored experimentally by means of two methodologies: wettability experiments (to determine the physical mechanisms of the interaction), and phase change experiments in larger crucibles (emulating a situation closer to final system operation). Wettability experiments have revealed that h-BN is the less reactive refractory in contact with liquid Si and Si-B alloys. Non-wetting behaviour is maintained up to temperatures of ~1650°C, which probably represents the upper limit for the containment of liquid Si and Si-B in h-BN crucibles. Importantly, h-BN has been revealed to be less wetted by liquid Si-B alloys than by pure Si, suggesting that boron addition to silicon PCM mitigates the dissolution of the BN crucible. The interaction of pure Si and Si-B alloys with graphite (C_{gr}) crucibles has been analyzed making relatively long (48h) tests at constant temperature and at cycling experiments. It was found that C_{gr} is transformed in SiC very quickly. This reaction is especially relevant in the pores of the C_{gr} crucible and at the PCM/crucible interface. However, this reaction will not be detrimental for operation. Besides, for large amounts of boron in the Si-B alloy, SiB₆ and B₄C phases are formed in the bulk and near the PCM/crucible interface, respectively. As a consequence, it was concluded that the eutectic Si-B alloy composition, having 3 wt% (8at. %) of boron and melting point of ~ 1380°C is the optimal, both in terms of latent heat (theoretically expected to be even larger than pure silicon), and to avoid the formation of borides such as SiB₆ and B₄C that end up consuming most of the boron in the alloy. Another activity has regarded the simulation the heat transfer process during melting and solidification of PCMs by using both 1-phase and 2-phase CFD models. Preliminary results show a good agreement with published experiments and analytical models. This model is being used to simulate the complex phase change process in the final LHTES system having realistic boundary conditions, such as non-adiabatic walls. Also, the CFD simulation of thermal insulation of the heat storage block has resulted in the optimal design for the thermal insulation cover. This consists of two or three layers (depending on the maximum operation temperature of the PCM) having a microporous fumed silica board as outer layer, and either graphite or alumina fibre mats for the inner ones. Vacuum is found to drastically improve thermal insulation of these layers.

Concerning the energy conversion block (WP3), a new VTEC setup has been already developed and installed, and it is currently being used to measure the thermionic I-V characteristic of converters. This setup has demonstrated the ability of reaching temperatures as high as 1850°C in UHV by means of laser heating. The cooling system of the VTEC setup has been simulated with CFD techniques assuming two kinds of coolants: a mixture of water and glycol ethylene, and liquid nitrogen. The results show that current VTEC cooling design based on water-glycol ethylene coolant is able to dissipate up to 200 W/cm² while keeping the upper part of the anode

at temperatures below 100°C. If liquid nitrogen were used, anode temperatures below 70°C could be feasible even at extremely high heat flux of 650 W/cm². The development of TIPV converters has also started by fabricating the separate elements: **i)** several thermionic cathode/emitters based on W substrates covered (using PLD) with thin layers (less than 20 nm) of borides (La-B, Ce-B) and nitrides (Al-N, C-N) have been experimentally investigated; being the ones based on La-B and Ce-B the ones showing the most promising results. The strong oxidation of these layers does not prevent the achievement of low workfunctions below ~ 3 eV; **ii)** anode coatings based on BaF₂ have been developed by magnetron sputtering and e-beam evaporation. Sputtering method enables the deposition of very thin layers (< 1 nm) with high precision, but results in a highly oxidized material that is probably preventing the achievement of a workfunction in the order of ~ 3 eV. On the other hand, e-beam evaporation has been proven to minimize oxidation, but makes difficult a precise control of the layer thickness. This problem is being solved by implementing a new e-beam evaporation system with a more accurate control of the deposition rate; **iii)** TPV cell semiconductor structures based on GaAs and InGaAs have been fabricated by MBE and conventionally photolithographic techniques, demonstrating very good electrical performance. The MBE grow of InGaAs structures have been carefully optimized to obtain a perfect match of the lattice constant of InGaAs layers to the InP substrate and have been able to produce more than 70 A/cm² and 20 W/cm² under flash illumination; **iv)** alumina microspacers have been already deposited by sputtering on GaAs substrates by means of a photolithographic processing of the surface. Concerning the final TIPV device fabrication, a new inverted three-terminal design is being implemented. Probably the most important advantage of this new design is the possibility of biasing the photovoltaic and thermionic sub-devices independently. Another benefit of this design is that the outermost anode layer is n-type semiconductor, which could enable the achievement of lower anode workfunction. Besides, it also enables locating the temperature-sensitive p-n junction near the cooling system. As a first step towards the development of this 3T device structure, interdigitated back contact TPV cells have been fabricated, demonstrating reasonable good performance for both GaAs and InGaAs semiconductor structures. TPV cell characterization has been conducted on a newly developed system that evaluates the energy balance in the cell, enabling the calculation of the TPV conversion efficiency. Thermionic experiments at UHV conditions and high temperature (1250°C) cathode (W/LaB₆) operation have been performed using both p-GaAs and n-GaAs anodes coated with BaF₂. This represents the first step towards the realization of the TIPV proof of concept experiment. First preliminary results show small (but non negligible) power generation.

Despite not starting until the end of 2018, some work has already started concerning the final proof of concept experiment (WP4) in order to anticipate the discussion about the final PoC experiment. According to preliminary simulations using quasi-1D analytical model, an inverted conical/pyramidal system is being selected for starting the design of the final LHTES prototype. The specific geometrical characteristics of this system are currently being defined. This design phase is taking into account the findings in WP2 and WP3, such as the use of optimal Si-B composition, the use of optimal refractory materials for the container, and the need of vacuum for thermal insulation.

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Introduction

AMADEUS project (www.amadeus-project.eu) aims to develop a new technology for energy storage based on ultra-high temperature (UHT) latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) materials and solid state energy converters [1]–[3]. The main motivation of this research is the very high latent heat of silicon and silicon-boron alloys (Figure 1) if compared with other kinds of phase change materials (PCM) such as molten salts. Energy densities beyond 1 kWh per liter are attainable, which is among the largest energy densities of any other storage technologies.

The main challenge concerning the use of these new PCMs is their ultra-high temperature (UHT) of fusion, which implies several concerns on the material compatibilities for the container, along with other issues such as thermal insulation and heat transfer during melting and solidification.

Another relevant aspect is the energy conversion of the latent heat into electricity at very high temperatures. In this regard, solid state energy converters based on radiative (rather than conductive) heat transfer mechanisms are being investigated in this project, i.e. thermionics and thermophotovoltaics (Figure 2). In particular, AMADEUS project investigates a new concept for heat-to-power conversion at UHT named hybrid thermionic photovoltaic (TIPV) converter [4] that directly converts into electricity both the electron and photon fluxes that irradiated by incandescent surfaces.

Figure 1. Latent heat of different materials. Red line represents Si-B alloys.

Figure 2. Energy conversion technologies as a function of maximum operation temperature [5].

Figure 3. AMADEUS project concept.

The final overall concept of the project is represented in Figure 3, which integrates both UHT-LHTES with TIPV energy conversion. The final goal is to develop a new kind of ultra-compact thermal energy storage (TES) device that might be used in a very broad range of applications, including solar thermal power generation, electric storage and cogeneration, waste heat recovery, space power, etc.

The technical work of the project is divided in two work-packages: WP2 (“Energy Storage Module”) deals with the PCM, the refractory container and thermal insulation. WP3 (“Energy Conversion Module”) deals with the TIPV solid state energy converter. WP4 (“Final Proof of Concept Experiment”) merge the outcomes of both work-packages to fabricate a final prototype that will demonstrate this new approach for energy storage.

Figure 4. Gantt Chart of the AMADEUS Project

After one year of development, AMADEUS project has progressed mainly in the work-packages WP2 and WP3. WP4 is scheduled to start in the month 23 (see Figure 4) but some preliminary activities have already started. In this report we briefly describe the main attainments of each WP during the first year of the project. This report is structured in tasks, as represented in Figure 4. More details on some specific tasks can be found in the already submitted deliverables (see Table 1).

Table 1. List of submitted (technical) deliverables after the first year of the project

Deliverable	Title	Public/Confidential	WP
D2.1	First Year Report on Data of Thermo-Physical Properties	Confidential	2
D3.1	Report on the emitter candidates	Confidential	3
D3.2	Upgrade of VTEC	Public	3
D3.3	Optimal design of cooling system	Confidential	3
D3.4	First report on advanced characterization of photovoltaic and thermionic devices	Confidential	3

Progress in WP2: Energy Storage Module

This WP targets objectives O1 (identify thermo-physical and mechanical properties of Si-B based alloys) and O2 (design of a novel PCM container configuration meeting the Si-B based alloys thermal properties). During this period, only one deliverable has been produced (D2.1, see Table 1) summarizing the progress on the determining the thermo-physical properties of materials (related to Task 2.1). In this section we partially describe this deliverable along with the activities belonging to the other tasks of this WP.

Task 2.1: Thermo-physical properties of materials

The Si-B system (Figure 5) is expected to present some key properties that are beneficial for thermal energy storage. Probably the most important is latent heat, but some other properties are important, such as volumetric expansion coefficient upon solidification or thermal conductivity/diffusivity, among others. Similarly, the refractory materials used for the container must meet some requirements, such as having high thermal conductivity. Despite the most important research on crucible material concerns its chemical interaction with the PCM (see Task 2.2), these materials are being also characterized in terms of thermophysical properties.

The Si-B system has been theoretically investigated by NTNU (Figure 6) using FactSage®. First, it is seen that melting temperatures of the Si-B eutectic (Si-3B wt%, m.p. of ~1380°C) is lower than that of the pure silicon (1414°C). In the hypereutectic region (B contents higher than ~4 wt% or 8 at.%), and above the solidus temperature, the Si-B PCM will contain a liquid Si-low B alloy in a mixture with solid silicon hexaboride (SiB₆). In this region, the incongruent solidification of the alloy (involving the formation of increasing amounts of SiB₆) results in a larger slope in the Enthalpy diagram (Figure 6), which means that the energy released from the formation of SiB₆ phase is delivered non-isothermally. This is the reason why the effect of adding Boron above the eutectic composition produces a lower latent heat at ~ 1380°C (Figure 6), and consequently, the maximum latent heat is obtained for the eutectic phase composition. It is important to notice that **latent heat of eutectic Si-3B wt% is larger than that of pure Si.**

Future work will consist on finding a third component that will move the eutectic to higher B contents for small additions and determine other properties for this system, especially the volume change. If this is not possible, the design of the system should address the heat flow only in the bottom.

Figure 5. Phase diagram of the Si-B system [6].

Figure 6. Enthalpy of fusion of Si-B alloys with different B contents (wt%)

FRI targets the experimental determination of thermo-physical properties of Si-B alloys and refractories at UHTs. For this, the following measurement techniques and facility available in FRI were used:

- Dilatometry (DIL). The examinations of thermal expansion changes were conducted by using Netzsch DIL 402C/4/G high-temperature dilatometer.
- Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The specific heat (C_p) measurements were performed by means of the differential scanning calorimeter Netzsch DSC 404 C/3/G Pegasus.
- Laser flash analysis (LFA). The thermal diffusivity coefficient (α) measurements were performed with the application of the Netzsch LFA 427 apparatus. The thermal conductivity (TC) was determined with the consideration of the radiation losses based on the non-linear regression and the Cape-Lehman model.
- Thermogravimetry (TG). The analysis of mass change as a function of time was carried out by using Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter coupled with 403C Aëolos QMS.

However, the characterization at temperatures up to 2000°C brings a lot of technological challenges. Among them, the most important one is a lack of already developed standard procedures and experimental setups for determining properties of Si and Si-B alloys at temperatures near their melting points. FRI has started trials on high temperature calorimetric studies (up to 1500°C) with the standard equipment, i.e. using alumina or graphite crucibles. These “standard” crucibles have proven a high reactivity with Si and Si-B alloys, avoiding the achievement of higher temperatures. In fact, using of these refractories for the UHT tests has resulted in a destruction of crucibles and a severe damage of apparatus.

Due to the lack of knowledge on the characterization of these materials at those UHTs, FRI had to look for a new crucible material that could be used in DSC experiments. For this reason, FRI performed the research on wettability/reactivity in various Si/refractories systems (**see Task 2.2, Subtask 2.2.1**). The most important requirement for the selection of refractories in UHT measurements is assumed to be their inertness with Si-based materials (i.e. the low reactivity and poor wettability). The results of the evaluations confirmed information reported in literature that the **h-BN is the only one ceramic that is non-wetted by molten Si at temperature near its melting point**. Furthermore, HT tests performed by FRI gave clear experimental evidence that this non-wetting behavior of Si/h-BN system is **maintained up to 1650°C**.

By having the experimentally established knowledge on the behavior of refractories, FRI purchased h-BN crucibles from the Netzsch Company for calorimetric studies of selected Si-based alloys. The current progress in the work associated with examinations of thermophysical properties is schematically shown in Table 1 (the following properties have been already examined or the examinations are in progress: coefficient of thermal expansion, thermal diffusivity, thermal conductivity, specific heat, heat capacity, latent heat, critical temperatures of phase transformations, density). The experimental procedures and testing conditions are listed in Table 2. The description of testing procedures for PCMs is provided in **Deliverable 2.1. (D2.1) “First year report on data of thermo-physical properties”**. Future work will continue with the experiments on

thermo-physical properties of PCMs candidates and refractories in order to fill the existed gaps in the Table 1.

Table 2. The current progress in the work associated with examinations of thermo-physical properties.

Materials	Sample name	DIL		Thermal diffusivity	Thermal conductivity	Cp	DSC (laten heat)	TG-QMS
		Δ/L_0	CTE					
Refractory materials	Si ₃ N ₄	Done	Done	In Progress	In Progress	In Progress	Not planned in the first year	Not planned in the first year
	ZrO ₂ (MgO)	In Progress						
	h-BN HeBoSint D100	In Progress						
	h-BN composite HeBoSint 0120	In Progress						
	Graphite	In Progress						
	SiC	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned		
	Al ₂ O ₃	In Progress						
	Porous zirconia	In Progress						
Alloy	Si UHP	Not planned in the first year						
	Si-2.5B							
	Si-8B							
	Si-13.5B							
	SiB ₆							

Done
Planned
In Progress
Not planned in the first year

DSC /(mW/mg)

Figure 7. DSC signal in mW/mg (non calibrated) upon solidification for several Si-B alloy compositions: Si (pink), Si-1B wt%(blue), Si-3B wt%(black), Si-5.7B wt%(green), Si-71B wt%(red). Black curve suggest a stronger exothermic effect for the eutectic Si_{0.92}B_{0.08} than for pure silicon (pink) at lower temperature, as expected from theoretical calculations in Figure 6.

Task 2.2: High temperature interaction of Si-B based alloys with refractory lining

A major relevant aspect of the new UHT-LHTES concept regards thermochemical compatibility of the selected Si-B PCMs with the container walls. In this project we are analyzing this complex issue by two methods: wettability tests (subtask 2.2.1, led by FRI) and reactivity and phase change tests (subtask 2.2.2, led by NTNU):

- **Subtask 2.2.1: Wettability tests**

FRI has performed experiments on wettability and reactivity of Si and Si-B alloys with selected refractories at temperatures up to 1750°C in order to understand the course of involved interfacial phenomena. First, the Si-xB ($x=1, 3, 5.7, 71$ wt%; $x=2.5, 8, 13.5, 86$ at.%, respectively) alloys were successfully fabricated from low purity elements by using the electric arc melting technique (Figure 8). Then, temperature dependent wetting behavior of pure Si and Si-xB alloys on selected ceramic substrates was examined by a sessile drop technique using contact heating procedure in the static inert gas (argon, $p = 850-900$ mbar) at different temperatures (1450°C; 1550°C; 1650°C; 1700°C and 1750°C). The structure and chemistry of solidified couples were examined by means of optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The most efforts were focused on a clarification of ultra-high temperature interfacial phenomena in the Si/h-BN system.

Figure 8. The macro-view of exemplary Si-B alloys having various B content, ($x=2.5, 8, 13.5, 86$ at.%, $x=1, 3, 5.7, 71$ wt%, respectively) fabricated by crucible less electric arc melting method.

Wettability of pure silicon

All examined popular commercially available polycrystalline ceramics (**SiC**, **ZrO₂** and **Si₃N₄**) show a high reactivity and good wettability with pure silicon at temperatures of 1450°C and higher. The recorded contact angles θ for these couples were generally below 90°, while the presence of sintering aids (of unknown species and quantities) additionally promotes a strong interaction with molten Si.

Hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) is the only one ceramic showing non-wetting ($\theta > 90^\circ$) with molten silicon at temperatures close to the melting point of Si. The results of our work showed for the first time the wetting behavior of the Si/h-BN couple upon heating to and cooling from ultrahigh temperature of 1750°C. It was demonstrated that increase of testing temperature improves wetting, and consequently the non-wetting-to-wetting transition ($\theta = 90^\circ$) takes place at around 1650°C. The contact angle of $90 \pm 5^\circ$ is maintained at temperatures up to 1750°C. However, an intensive drop vibration accompanied with periodic change in the contact angle values of $\pm 5^\circ$ points toward a lack of complete thermodynamic and chemical equilibrium in the system under conditions of this study. During cooling, the contact angle gradually increases with temperature decrease showing wetting-to-dewetting transition ($\theta > 90^\circ$) at about the same temperature of 1650°C. Due to this behavior, this is **our practical recommendation that working temperature of pure-Si based LHTES system should not exceed 1650°C when h-BN is used as the crucible material** for melting and long-term storage of liquid pure Si.

The wetting behavior of the Si/h-BN couple during heating to and cooling from ultrahigh temperature of 1750°C is controlled by the substrate dissolution/reprecipitation mechanism. The dissolution of h-BN substrate in the Si specimen and a gradual saturation of molten silicon with boron and nitrogen (through solid and liquid state diffusion) changes the chemical composition of the initially pure Si drop to Si-B-N alloy at high temperatures, followed by release of overbalanced nitrogen from the drop through liquid/gas and liquid/solid interfaces. Substrate dissolution in the Si drop leads to the formation of the crater inside the substrate under the drop. During cooling, the h-BN phase reprecipitates from the Si-B-C-N melt at the substrate-side interface and large h-BN platelets grow and fill the crater. This process is accompanied with the removal of the Si-B-C-N melt from the regions between the h-BN platelets due to their dewetting at temperature below 1650°C. This phenomenon was directly confirmed by microscopic observations of the dewetting zone that was revealed during cooling and solidification of the Si drop.

As opposite to data reported in the literature for $T \leq 1500^\circ\text{C}$, the formation of silicon nitride as discontinuous interfacial layer in the Si/h-BN system, is not confirmed by the results of our experimental examinations of the couple produced at 1750°C. Two possible reasons are suggested to be responsible for a lack of Si_3N_4 phase: 1) a presence of carbon contamination in the h-BN substrate promotes the formation of few SiC crystals instead of Si_3N_4 layer, as the interfacial product under presently examined testing conditions; 2) Si_3N_4 is not stable at ultrahigh temperature thus even it might be formed during step heating at lower temperatures, this phase disappears at the last step corresponding to the highest temperature of 1750°C. Moreover, during cooling from 1750°C, the drop is already oversaturated with boron while overbalanced nitrogen is released thus making impossible the formation of the Si_3N_4 phase under conditions of this study.

Wettability of Si-B alloys

Concerning wettability of Si-B alloys, two types of commercial refractories were selected as the substrates: the “pure” h-BN and the h-BN based composite. It was found that both refractories show a lack of wettability in the whole tested temperature range with all selected alloys (the measured contact angle was $\theta > 130^\circ$). The more stable behavior in contact with molten Si-B alloys, reflected by higher θ values and a lack of drop vibration during the high temperature exposition, was observed for the h-BN based composite substrate.

Figure 9. The wetting kinetic for the sessile drop experiment of the Si/h-BN couple.

Table 3. A few examples of contact angles measured for different PCM/refractory combinations.

droplet	Si	Si	Si	Si	Si	Si-13.5B	Si-13.5B
substrate	h-BN	h-BN +SiC+ZrO ₂	h-BN spray/SiC	SiC	ZrO ₂	h-BN	h-BN +SiC+ZrO ₂
T[°C]	θ [°]						
1450	115	132	126	43	100	145	153
1550	97	123	120	45	96	143	150
1650	94	118	115	44	96	136	147
1700	92	115	114	44	92	134	144
1750	90	110	97	0	92	131	136

By comparing the results of wettability tests at temperature up to 1750°C obtained for ultra-high purity Si and Si-B alloys with h-BN ceramics, it might be concluded that **the alloying of Si with boron decreases wetting in the Si/h-BN systems**. Under the same testing conditions, higher contact angle values were recorded for each Si-B alloy/h-BN couple than for Si/h-BN counterparts. This finding is in line with our previous conclusions that the wettability/reactivity mechanism in the Si/h-BN is mostly controlled by the dissolution of h-BN substrate. Thus, in the view of these findings, it is also reasonable to conclude that the addition of boron simply decreases the dissolution of boron nitride in molten Si. Nevertheless, this statement will be further confirmed by microscopic evaluations of the interfaces in solidified sessile drop Si-B/h-BN couples.

Regarding predicted applications in LHTES systems, **both h-BN-based refractories might be considered as possible candidates for container materials** for melting and storage of Si-B-X alloys. However, both interfacial phenomena and thermal cycling behavior need to be experimentally evaluated. Future work will continue the research on the interfacial phenomena in Si-B/h-BN systems at temperature up to 1750°C: A detailed evaluation of the role of SiC and ZrO₂ constituents/sintering aids in high temperature behavior of the HeBoSint® O120 material in contact with Si-B alloys. More wettability tests on Si-B alloys/refractories at temperature up to 1500°C (i.e. Si-B/Si₃N₄) will be also conducted. Thermal cycling tests of Si-B alloys with various h-BN substrates will be conducted by using sessile drop method and differential scanning calorimetry in order to examine the cycling evolution of latent heat during melting/solidification steps. Furthermore, non-destructive computed tomography analyses of Si-B/refractories couples after the thermal cycling experiments will be carried out.

- **Subtask 2.2.2: Reactivity and phase changes tests**

The stability of Si and Si-B alloys with C, Si₃N₄, SiO₂ and BN crucibles have been analyzed from the theoretical point of view by NTNU using FactSage®. First studies on

the interaction of Si-B with the container made of SiO_2 predict that B will dissolve the crucible ($3\text{SiO}_2 + 4\text{B} = 3\text{Si} + 2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$), being the mixture of $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ probably liquid. Besides, $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Si}$ will react to SiO gas. Therefore, **SiO_2 cannot be used for containing liquid Si-B alloys.** In the case of a crucible made of silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) the interaction will produce a BN phase at the interface. This BN layer could behave as a protective coating impeding further dissolution of the crucible; thus, **Si_3N_4 could be an interesting option.** This is the same situation for BN crucibles. With a SiC crucible, it is observed that SiC is in stable phase with Si but B_4C will be produced at the interface to SiC crucible.

Figure 10. Phase-change tests conducted in C_{gr} crucibles with different Si-B alloy compositions.

Figure 11. SEM images of Si-B alloys (produced in C_{gr} crucibles) with different compositions: (a) Si-5 wt%B, (b) Si-15 wt%B. SiB_6 phase is only present for larger amounts of B.

Short-duration experiments

First experiments consisted on melting Si-B alloys on C_{gr} crucibles and maintaining the Si-B alloys melted during a short time of $\sim 2\text{h}$ (Figure 10). These experiments were carried out with Si-B alloys having 0 – 25% wt% of B and the test temperatures ranged from 1450°C to 1750°C . Some examples of the obtained results are shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12. First, it is observed that for large B contents, not only SiB_3 but also SiB_6 phase is present in the alloy (Figure 11). Notice that, under thermodynamic equilibrium conditions (Figure 5), SiB_6 should be present for temperatures in between $\sim 1270^\circ\text{C}$ and

~1850°C. The presence of SiB_6 phase at room temperature is probably due to the rapid cooling, far from thermodynamic equilibrium conditions that avoid the full interaction of this phase with the rest of alloy.

Figure 12. SEM images and measured composition profiles of the interface between Si-B and C_{gr} for two Si-B compositions: (top) Si-2wt% B, (bottom) Si-8wt% B. Experiments were carried out up to 1750°C. For the larger B content (bottom), a double layer of SiC/ B_4C is formed at the interface. For the lower amount of B, only SiC is formed.

Regarding the interface between the alloy and the crucible, it is found that a thin **SiC** layer is created in the interface. At high B contents **B_4C** layer will be also produced at the surface of the crucible. This layer probably comes from the reaction of SiC with B near the crucible surface. When B_4C is produced it consumes a lot of the B in the alloy and the B content in the alloy will decrease. Notice that some of the B_4C has been found also in the alloy phase (Figure 11). **At low B contents, (less than 5 wt%) SiB_6 and B_4C will not be present and the alloy will be relatively clean.**

Long duration and cycling experiments

Several kinds of experiments were conducted on the Si-B eutectic alloy composition (Si-3B wt. %) consisting on keeping the alloy melted during longer periods and performing cycles. The longest experiment duration was 48 h. It is seen that the **Si will penetrate**

the crucible and produce SiC quite fast, and after that the reactions are very slow. The Si penetration is very dependent on the porosity, and hence a **dense crucible is needed**. Besides, as observed in the previous experiments, on the surface of the crucible a dense SiC barrier layer will be produced, which will decrease the further crucible reactions. This layer may rarely leave the crucible surface and be found in the alloy. However, in the experiments the alloy is still quite clean from SiC at the eutectic composition, and we observed that cycling of temperature, above the melting temperature, is not affecting the alloy composition.

Figure 13. Interface after 48h of interaction at 1550°C. Pores in C_{gr} will be filled with SiC.

It is hence **suggested that one works within the area of the eutectic composition (8 at%, B = 3 wt% B)**, e.g. between 2-5 wt% B in the alloy due to no production of the solid particles of SiB_6 and B_4C . No solid particles will:

- Increase the fusion of heat per volume unit
- No B will be lost to the B_4C solid particles.
- The solidification is easier to control is no solid particles is present, e.g. from the bottom of the crucible.
- Viscosity and other parameters will be according to the melt only.

Concerning crucible material, **both dense carbon and SiC crucibles could be used as container material**. As both carbon and SiC wet the alloy, over time a thin silicon layer may cover the crucible. In other processes this has been stopped by adding a non-wetting band in the top of the crucible (e.g. h-BN).

Task 2.3: Heat transfer and thermo-mechanical interaction between vessel and Si-B based alloys

CERTH/CPERI has analyzed the solidification process of a PCM inside a sealed vessel using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). The numerical model main features are:

- A simplified 1phase and an advanced 2Phase CFD model applied in the ANSYS Fluent platform (v17.1)
- Solid phase is captured using the enthalpy/porosity method that can properly describe the unsteady heat transfer mechanisms during the freezing.
- Expansion of the PCM during freezing is included
- Gas/PCM interface, contained inside the shell, is captured with the volume of fluid (VOF) approach.
- liquid natural convection and dendrites formation through the implicit use of Amush.

For the case investigated, the PCM is pure silicon with a high melting point (1680 K) and the vessel has the shape of truncated pyramid. Initially, before its freezing/expansion, the PCM fills 85% of the vessel. The rest of the container is filled with an inert gas. First, the results of the simplified 1Phase CFD model were compared against the ones obtained from the respective model developed by Veeraragavan et al. [7] in OpenFoam (meltFoam) solver and analytical 1D model by Datas et al. [1], in order to enhance the solidification CFD model validity at different solvers. This 1Phase model neglects the PCM volumetric change during its freezing and the presence of the gas inside the shell. As a further step, the advanced 2Phase model was applied and results of all models were compared and reported in reference [8]. Added to this, a grid dependency study was conducted in the advanced 2Phase model, by comparing numerical results under three grid densities, i.e. coarse, medium and a grid with adaptive local refinement. For the refinement technique, in-house user-defined functions (UDFs) were implemented. In all cases tested the upper and side walls of the tank were assumed adiabatic. Finally, a custom-UDF was applied to calculate iteratively at each time step the temperature dependent heat flux at the emitter surface.

From the CFD analysis it was revealed that for most of the simulation time, results of the advanced Fluent 2Phase model virtually coincide with that of the Fluent 1Phase, OpenFoam and Analytical 1-D model. During the silicon solidification inside the sealed truncated pyramid, **the dominant heat transfer mechanism is thermal conduction**. Thus, neglecting in the 1D model of phenomena, such as the liquid natural convection and PCM expansion, is expected to play a minor effect on the temperature profile prediction inside the casing for most of the solidification process. Dendrite formation was more pronounced in the 2Phase model. The advanced CFD 2Phase model can be applied in more complicated cases, or in the case of more complex and promising designs, where multiphase applications, characterized by high gradients of different properties are included. Using this model, we get a more realistic representation of the solidification process. In addition, influential operating parameters that cannot be easily predicted from 1D models, such as pressure distribution, thermal stresses, thermal losses etc., can be described in detail by such CFD model.

Figure 14. Comparison between the four models used to describe the solidification of the truncated-pyramid geometrical configuration of the system.

Future work will consist on the study of the PCM solidification/melting process, by means of the advanced 2Phase CFD model, with incorporation of heat losses in the inverted truncated pyramid container, the parametric study on the heat losses variation under different emitter surfaces and container volumes; the thorough investigation of the design effect on induced stresses-strains in the vessel, and the simulation of the solidification/melting process of the boron-silicon mixture.

Task 2.4: Advanced thermal insulation

USTUTT has explored suitable thermal insulation materials (TIM) and infrared reflecting foils for the required temperature range. Main researched parameters were maximum long-term service temperature, thermal conductivity and emissivity for the required temperature range and prices. To estimate the thermal conductivity of TIM in argon and in high vacuum, simple approximations based on measured values (taken from literature for some TIM) have been utilized. Fitting curves of the temperature dependent measured and approximated thermal conductivities were used as input parameters in thermal simulation studies.

A potential study on multi-foil insulation has been carried out comparing firstly the calculated heat flux through TIM with the calculated heat flux through this multi-foil insulation and secondly comparing the material costs. This potential study showed that **the application of TIM is more promising than a multi-foil insulation in terms of costs, feasibility, handling and effectiveness.**

Thermal simulations were carried out, using the software COMSOL Multiphysics, to determine the required thermal insulation thickness (and thus material costs), heat losses and cooling rates dependent on the insulation materials and applied gases. The simulation model (Figure 15) contains the thermal energy store (TES) in shape of a truncated cone, two to three insulation layers for different TIMs and a gap between the TES and the TIM. TES temperature has been varied between 2 000 °C and 1 500 °C.

Figure 15. Representation of the thermal insulation strategy comprising two to three layers of TIMs. Calculations are made for a fixed TES size represented in the figure and with the heat transfer mechanisms named therein.

Further simulations are in progress wherein the size of the TES has been varied. The thermal conductivity of selected TIMs is shown in Figure 16.

The simulation results (Figure 17) pointed out that a very low thermal conductivity of the TIM is very important to reduce costs and size of the thermal insulation. The lowest thermal conductivities can be reached by using TIM in vacuum atmosphere. The simulation results show heat loss rates and costs for the corresponding combination of TIM. Thus a decision on the insulation concept for the prototype can be done based on these parameters. **Both low PCM temperature and high TIM vacuum reduces heat losses and TIM costs.** For instance, with a TES temperature of 1 500 °C the heat losses can be reduced by a factor of around 3 compared to a TES temperature of 2 000 °C and the same TIM costs.

Furthermore, USTUTT did measurements of the thermal conductivity of three relevant thermal insulation materials: graphite fiber mat “Sigratherm® GFA”, alumina fiber mat “CTM 1600” and microporous fumed silica board “WDS® Ultra”. The measurements were carried out in a guarded hot plate apparatus (GHPA) in air atmosphere and in a temperature range between 10 °C and 100 °C. The measurement results have been used for validation of manufacturer data in this temperature range and of analytical heat transfer models for thermal insulation materials. For CTM 1600 the measured thermal conductivity in the GHPA of USTUTT at 48.4 °C was only 1.5 % (0.6 mW/(m·K)) lower than the manufacturer data at 50 °C. This deviation is within the measurement uncertainty of the GHPA of typically ± 3 %. For WDS Ultra at 67.8 °C the measured value in the USTUTT GHPA was 35 % (7 mW/(m·K)) higher than the extrapolated fitting curve of the manufacturer data. The deviation is probably a result of different conditioning of the samples. At USTUTT the samples are previously stored under laboratory conditions (ambient temperature: (23 ± 5) °C, relative humidity: (50 ± 10) %). Manufacturers often dry their samples before measuring. Fumed silica is a hydrophilic material and adsorbs up to 2 weight-% water, which increases the thermal conductivity significantly. The more realistic conditions for the prototype (proof of concept) however are laboratory conditions. At higher temperatures, the water desorbs from the material. Thus, the manufacturer data at higher temperatures can be considered more realistic for the prototype. For Sigratherm® GFA there were no manufacturer data available from measurements in air atmosphere. The results of the measurements will also be used for a comparison with the thermal conductivity measurements in a laser flash apparatus at FRI. FRI will carry out thermal conductivity measurements for TIM at higher temperatures.

The recommendation for the thermal insulation material consists on a system of two/three layers, depending on the final temperature range:

- Inside insulation layer (2000 °C – 1000 °C): **Graphite fiber mat “Sigratherm® GFA”**: quite low thermal conductivity, inert gas or vacuum required, not rigid → fixing may be required, lower price than rigid ceramic boards (17 €/dm³)
- Inside/middle insulation layer (1600 °C – 1000 °C): **Alumina fiber mat “Alumina mat”**: low thermal conductivity, no inert gas or vacuum required, not rigid → fixing may be required, lower price (7 €/dm³), high shipping costs (800 €)

- Outside insulation layer (< 1000 °C): **Fumed silica board “WDS® Ultra”**: very low thermal conductivity, no inert gas or vacuum needed, rigid → stand-alone shell, low price (2.5 €/dm³).

Figure 16. Thermal conductivity of selected TIMs as a function of temperature.

Figure 17. Calculated heat loss as a function of total insulation thickness of different TIM combinations. All combinations use fumed silica board for the outer cover.

Task 2.5: Fabrication of the final heat storage block and cycling experiments

Although not scheduled for this stage of the Project, UPM has already started doing some preliminary developments concerning the final heat storage block fabrication. Main activities consisted on manufacturing the oven structure and instrumentation system for performing preliminary heating experiments, combined with thermophotovoltaic (TPV) generation. The temperature of the crucible is measured along with the main TPV cell parameters during operation (i.e. current, voltage, maximum power). The cell temperature was estimated by means of thermocouple, demonstrating TPV cell operation temperatures below 50°C. Still further experiments are needed to determine this temperature with greater precision. The main objective of this activity was to identify any eventual risks for the manufacturing of the final heat storage block. The main issues found were related to the crucible material that looked damaged after the experiments. Future experiments will improve this design by using better thermal insulation and crucible materials. These experiments will serve for getting hands experience that will be taken into account in the next steps of the design of the system.

Figure 18. Preliminary prototype for demonstrating thermophotovoltaic power generation from radiant heat in the LHTES arrangement (a,b) pictures of the prototype, (c) system under operation with a water-cooled TPV cell on the top and alumina fiber mat for thermal insulation.

Figure 19. Preliminary results for the thermophotovoltaic power generation in the prototype of Figure 18. A 1.5 cm² GaSb TPV cell (provided by JX Crystals) have been used in this first experiment. (a) crucible temperature as a function of time, (b) photocurrent density as a function of time, (c) photocurrent density as a function of temperature.

Progress in WP3: Energy Conversion Module

This WP targets objective O3 (Demonstrate the proof of concept of a thermionic-photovoltaic converter). During this period, four deliverables has been produced (D3.1-D3.4, see Table 1). In this section we partially describe these deliverables along with a brief the description of other activities belonging to this WP.

Task 3.1: Development of the thermionic emitter

- **Subtask 3.1.1: Selection of substrate(s) for thermionic emitter**

This activity was successfully completed by CNR with the timely release of Deliverable 3.1. The main materials identified as substrate for the thermionic emitter are summarized in Table 4. The main three requirements are: high melting point and high electrical and thermal conductivities. Also, a linear thermal expansion coefficient to that of the emitting layer is desirable. According to the data shown in Table 4, **tungsten (W) was selected for the first thermionic emitter developments.**

Table 4. Selected substrate materials for the thermionic emitter.

Substrate	Melting point (°C)	Electric resistivity @ 2000°C (μΩ cm) [Refs. 1-4]	Thermal conductivity @ 2000°C (W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹) [Refs. 5-6]	Linear thermal expansion coefficient (x10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹) [Refs. 7-9]
Mo	2617	53	138	7.3 (@2000°C)
W	3410	67	152	6.5 (@2000°C)
Ta	2996	88	62	7.7 (@1700°C)
Re	3186	105	43	7.0 (@1700°C)

- **Subtask 3.1.2: Development of thermionic emitting layer**

The thermionic emitting layer must provide a low work function on the surface of the emitter, to facilitate the emission of electrons. Other requirements are high melting point and linear expansion coefficient similar to that of the substrate. Among the several emitter layers that were identified in Deliverable D3.1 (see Table 5), **nanostructured films of LaB₆ and CeB₆ were selected to be deposited by PLD on the W substrate.**

Table 5. Selected emitting layer materials.

Material	Melting point (°C)	Work function (eV) [Refs. 10-15]	Linear thermal expansion coefficient ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [Refs. 16-22]
LaB ₆	2210	2.6	5.75(@1000°C) 8.7 (@2000°C)
CeB ₆	2552	2.5	6.67 (@1000°C)
Amorphous CN _x	>2000	0.64 - 3.81	2 – 9 (@140°C)
AlN:H	>2000	< 3	5.5 – 6 (@1000°C)
SrVO ₃	~2300	1.86	18 (@950°C)
SrZrO ₃	~2700	1.1	11 (@1100°C)
Nanodiamond:H Diamond:H	>3500 (dependent on pressure)	1.7 (<780 °C) 2.7-3.5 (>780 °C)	2 - 3.5 (@300 °C)

The development of lanthanum boride films of thickness <20 nm was carried on by CNR by using pulsed laser deposition (PLD). Morphologic characterizations with SEM and AFM as well as chemical ones by XPS and EDS were performed to determine their physical properties as a function of deposition parameters (substrate temperature, gas atmosphere, etc.). These techniques were integrated to others aiming at quantifying the coating work function at room and high temperatures. UPS and direct measurement of thermionic emission up to 1000 °C (under extension up to 2000 °C with the VTEC upgrade) were employed to determine this surface property value that is essential for the AMADEUS application. An amount of oxygen was found to be unintentionally incorporated within the films owing to the high reactivity of the La atoms, which led to a composition typical of oxy-boride films (Table 6). However, even though the undesired composition, **the work function of the lanthanum (oxy)boride films was found as low as 2.8 and 3.0 eV by thermionic emission measurements (Figure 20) and UPS, respectively.**

Other materials such as AlN, CN_x, and cerium (oxy)boride films were developed by PLD, and found to be characterized by minimum work functions measured by thermionic emission of 3.2, 1.6, 3.0 eV, respectively. The extremely low work function of CN_x is not exploitable for enhancing the thermionic performance, since it was found together with a too low Richardson constant (5-orders of magnitude lower than that of the other emitters), that is detrimental for the electron emission capability. The optimization of their physical properties in terms of uniformity, homogeneity, and thermal stability is an ongoing activity.

Table 6. Compositional analysis of the cathode coatings

Sample	X/Y (%at.)	X	Y	Oxygen/Y (%at.)	Composition (%at.)	crystallinity
La-B	3.09	B	La	6.67	La _{10.37} B _{20.51} O _{69.12}	polycrystalline
Ce-B	2.98	B	Ce	6.48	Ce _{9.56} B _{28.49} O _{61.95}	polycrystalline
Al-N	0.17	N	Al	1.73	Al _{34.46} N _{5.96} O _{59.58}	amorphous
C-N	0.16	N	C	6.04	C _{13.8} N _{2.28} O _{83.82}	amorphous

Sample	A* (A/cm ² K ²)	Φ (eV)	J @ 2000 °C (A/cm ²)
La-B	10.14	2.82	3.19
Ce-B	9.63	2.96	1.34
Al-N	77.30	3.19	2.83
C-N	5.47×10 ⁻⁵	1.58	0.023

Richardson-Dushman equation:

$$J = A_R T^2 \exp(-\Phi/K_B T)$$

Figure 20. (a) thermionic current-temperature characteristics for different emitting layers and (b) corresponding parameters fitting the Richardson-Dushman equation.

Task 3.2: Development of the TPV cell

The first TPV cell development at UPM was based on GaAs semiconductor (Figure 21). Despite GaAs bandgap (~ 1.4 eV) is too large for TPV applications, these cells were developed first to kick-start the thermionic experiments on relevant anode substrates at CNR. First, the cell structure was grown by MBE, and then the PV cells were manufactured using conventional photolithography techniques. The I-V curves show a very good behavior, with open circuit voltages above 1V. Some of these structures have been delivered to CNR, where they have been coated with BaF₂ for eventually performing TIPV experiments.

GaAs (AA06)

500 nm p++ GaAs 8e18-1e20
5 nm p+ AlAs 8e18
5 nm p+ GaAs 8e18
30 nm p+ Al _{0.5} Ga _{0.5} As 4e18
900 nm p+ GaAs 2e18
5000 nm n+ GaAs 2e17
200 nm n+ Al _{0.33} Ga _{0.67} As 1.33e18
525 nm n-GaAs 2e18
N++ GaAs substrate

Figure 21. GaAs PV cells (left) design of the structure, (right-top) pictures of the PV cell and the full semiconductor wafer with the PV cell structure, (right-bottom) measured I-V curves at two different illumination levels.

40 nm p++In _{0.53} Ga _{0.47} As 5e19
360 nm p+In _{0.53} Ga _{0.47} As 8e17
470 nm n-In _{0.53} Ga _{0.47} As 2e17
30 nm n-In _{0.53} Ga _{0.47} As 2e17
200 nm n+ In _{0.53} Ga _{0.47} As 3e18
300um N++ InP 3e18

Figure 22. (left) First InGaAs TPV cell structure grown on InP substrate by MBE at UPM. (right) I-V curves under variable irradiance conditions, emulating the operation under real conditions of UHT irradiance illumination.

Figure 23. Alternative designs of the TIPV anode a) two-terminal (2T) design with the p-n junction placed at the anode upper surface, b) three-terminal (3T) design with the p-n junction placed at the anode bottom part. In both cases, the (thicker) substrate is the N-type semiconductor.

In the second half of the year UPM has grown an $\text{In}_{0.53}\text{Ga}_{0.47}\text{As}$ TPV cell semiconductor structure on n-type InP substrates. Preliminary results revealed a lattice mismatch between the substrate and the InGaAs layers, which has resulted in a bad morphology of the structure. Despite a first InGaAs TPV cell has been manufactured showing photovoltaic behavior, the performance was far from being optimal. After some calibrations of the MBE system (in particular focusing on precisely controlling the In/Ga ratio), UPM successfully managed to fabricate optimal InGaAs structures. TPV cells fabricated from these structures have shown fantastic performance both in terms of open circuit voltage and fill factor. The measurement of these cells under flash illumination enables the measurement of the I-V curves under variable irradiance conditions, emulating its behavior under high irradiance fluxes at high temperatures. Results are shown in Figure 22, showing the ability to produce **photocurrent densities above 60 A/cm² and electrical power densities beyond 20 W/cm²**.

In parallel, CNR verified by UPS that **heavily doped p-type GaAs shows a work function of 4.7 ± 0.1 eV, whereas n-type one of 3.5 ± 0.2 eV**. This indicates that heavily n-doped semiconductors could represent a more efficient solution for a lower work function anode. In order to take advantage of the lower workfunction of n-type semiconductors, UPM has designed a **new 3-terminal (3T) inverted TIPV design** in which both positive and negative electric contacts are made in the front side of the cell and the TPV cell is illuminated from the rear (Figure 23). In this arrangement, the thick n-type InP semiconductor substrate directly faces the emitter. Notice that InP is transparent to IR light in the relevant portion of the spectrum. This new design has some important advantages with respect to the previous 2T design:

- N-type anode may enable lower surface workfunction;
- Anode surface is completely flat (no terminals) thus enabling a simpler implementation of coatings and micro-spacers by CNR and IONVAC;
- Thermally sensitive p-n junction is located nearer to the cooling system; thus, it is expected to be colder;

- Enables the independent biasing of both thermionic and photovoltaic outputs; thus, enabling a more thorough characterization and the possibility of biasing both sub-devices at the maximum power point conditions simultaneously.

UPM has implemented this new 3T design in three different PV cell semiconductor structures: two InGaAs-based (commercial) and one GaAs-based (grown by MBE at UPM, Figure 21). These devices have shown relatively good performance under low irradiance (~ 1 sun) conditions, as observed in Figure 24. Larger (lower) open-circuit voltage (short-circuit current) is obtained for the GaAs devices, as expected.

Figure 24. (left) I-V characteristics of interdigitated back contact (IBC) (T)PV cells made of the three different semiconductor structures: one based on GaAs and two based on InGaAs; (right) an example of fabricated 1x1cm IBC (T)PV cell having both contacts in the same side.

Task 3.3: Development of the thermionic collector coating and micro-spacers

This task is subdivided in two subtasks: development of collector coatings (led by CNR) and developing micro-spacers (led by IONVAC).

• Subtask 3.3.1: Development of collector coating(s)

By means of magnetron sputtering, Barium-based coatings were developed on the p-GaAs substrates provided by UPM (work function measured by XPS of 4.7 ± 0.1 eV). Barium was selected for its higher temperature resistance than the cesium (and its compounds). **BaO** coatings were developed, but resulted in a high degradation in air (aggregation of BaO into islands) and in a consequent work function reduction of the BaO-coated GaAs only to 4.4 and 4.2 eV.

Figure 25. Deposition of BaF₂ anode coatings on p-GaAs by magnetron sputtering. (left) thickness as a function of deposition time, (right) resultant work function as a function of thickness. Work function of 3.05 eV is obtained for 0.15 nm BaF layer on p-GaAs. Oxidation is probably hampering the achievement of lower workfunctions.

An alternative was represented by the BaF₂ coatings (< 3 nm thickness), developed by magnetron sputtering (CNR) and e-beam evaporation (IONVAC). The films developed by sputtering show a work function approaching (3.0 ± 0.1) eV in the case of a p-type GaAs substrate for an optimal thickness of 0.15 nm (Figure 25), but no further reductions were found by changing the other relevant deposition parameters of inert gas pressure and RF power, the reason probably being the incorporation of large amounts of oxygen in the film. Conversely, e-beam evaporation was found to allow a better stoichiometry and significant reduction of oxygen inclusion in the growing film during the deposition process. However, the process resulted in a too high layer thickness (~350 nm for 30 sec process) that hampers work function measurements due to charging effects. Future work will consist on achieving a more accurate control of the e-beam evaporation at low e-beam powers. Alternatively, the evaporation of Cs and Ba on the TPV cell directly in the VTEC characterization setup is being also considered.

- **Subtask 3.3.2: Development of micro-spacers (month 1-15)**

The development of alumina and zirconia films were carried on by IONVAC by applying the close-to-room-temperature recipe (max 85 °C) on p- and n-type GaAs substrates, compatible with no degradation of photoresist and III-V semiconductor substrates. Alumina films were presently preferred to zirconia for the higher electric resistivity. Repeatable alumina microstructures, with shape to be improved, were developed both on GaAs and Si wafers by applying photolithographic patterns provided by CNR (

Figure 26). Their structure and composition was measured by XRD. The post annealing procedure of the developed microspacers is under optimization under ultra-high temperatures in the VTEC by analyzing the influence of annealing temperatures and

time on the mechanical stability of the microstructures, as well as the long-term operating behavior at such temperature range.

Figure 26. SEM images of alumina microspheres.

Figure 27. CFD simulation of the cooling system (a) water coolant, (b) liquid nitrogen coolant, (c) temperature profile in the anode assembly, (d) 3D representation of temperature profile.

- **Subtask 3.3.3: Development of micro-spacers on collector**

This task is not presently active.

Task 3.4: Cooling system design and optimization

In order to predict the anode temperature and related thermal gradient as a function of cooling conditions, CERTH performed advanced Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations on simplified but realistic CAD designs of the VTEC anode holder and components, designed and provided by IONVAC. CNR and UPM provided CERTH with the input power of the anode as a function of temperature in the range 1500 – 2000 °C, derived from the expected physical parameters of the cathodic component. Several scenarios were simulated by CERTH in the aforementioned temperature range, investigating mainly two liquid coolants (water + glycol ethylene, liquid nitrogen) under varying coolant flow rates and inlet temperatures. The objective was to avoid surpassing the temperature limit of 100 °C for the anode surface. Water + ethylene at the maximum flow rate as cooling solution is found to satisfy the objective only for input fluxes < 200 W/cm² (Figure 27), whereas the liquid nitrogen solution is compliant with the objective for every cathode temperature and flow rate. However, the choice of the latter entails the risk of strong expansion due to nitrogen boiling inside the copper tank and in view of that several practical measures need to be undertaken, to avoid these issues (possible increase of tank pressure). Additional cooling strategies and design concepts were also suggested. The whole of this activity is included in the Deliverable 3.4.

Task 3.5: Experimental Characterization

- **Subtask 3.5.1 Upgrade of the characterization system**

This activity was successfully completed by IONVAC and CNR with the timely release of Deliverable 3.2. The new developed Vacuum & Temperature Electronic Characterization (VTEC) setup (Figure 28) aims at achieving ultra-high temperature conditions (≤ 2000 °C) for testing of the TIPV technology under development. The activity started with the design of an additional vacuum chamber to be integrated to the present VTEC. A high power diode laser (LuOcean P2 with 250 W, 808 nm wavelength) is used for reaching ultra-high-temperature conditions at ultra-high-vacuum conditions ($<10^{-8}$ mbar). Anode and cathode holders were specifically and accurately designed to meet the specifications of high and low thermal conductivity towards the ambience, respectively. Starting from the raw materials, IONVAC fabricated every single component. The cathode holder was made in tantalum, supported by a BN component. The anode holder is made of copper equipped by a specific cooling system (compatible also with the use of liquid nitrogen). Additional functions given to the system were a translational stage able to control the inter-electrode distance with a sub-micrometer resolution, a window for laser injection with a very low reflectance ($<0.1\%$) at the laser wavelength, a thermal evaporation source for depositing in situ thin coatings, a vacuum gate for a possible separated differential pumping, an inlet for gases (methane, cesium vapour).

Figure 28. Upgrade of the VTEC setup. (a) Full system already operative at CNR, (b) CAD design developed by IONVAC, (c) CAD design of the anode holder, (d) Picture of the anode holder.

- **Subtask 3.5.2 Characterization of thermionic and photovoltaic devices**

After the completion and installation of the VTEC upgrade, ultra-high-temperature characterization of single components started at CNR labs. **The achievement of about 1850 °C was successfully performed** during the testing before the final installation (Figure 29), but this temperature was not overcome for allowing safe operations (in order to maintain ultra-high vacuum conditions during measurements). The laser power dynamics seems to indicate that 2000 °C can be reached at the maximum (Figure 29).

The thermionic emission measurements were conducted up to 1600 °C. The first characterizations have been carried out under not optimal conditions, due to geometrical constraints which obliged to fix the inter-electrode distance not shorter than 500 μm .

This issue is going to be resolved thanks to a slight modification of the heights of the boron nitride insulators (for the electrical contact and the thermocouple on the anode holder) and of the tungsten (W) cathode substrate. Such gap between the electrodes induced severe limitations due to space-charge, which hugely limited the collected current density.

First experiments were conducted using a lanthanum oxy-boride emitting layer and an anode with a known work function (Au, 5.1 eV). This represents case A in Table 7, which is not an ideal configuration because the cathode work function is lower than the anode one ($\Phi_C < \Phi_A$). Subsequent experiments were conducted on both p-type and n-type GaAs substrates (cases B and C, respectively), representing the first step towards a TIPV configuration. The device performance was evaluated by performing I-V measurements (Figure 30) trying to maintain the same inter-electrode distance of $\sim 800 \mu\text{m}$, and emitter temperature of 1260°C .

Figure 29. (left) Cathode temperature as a function of the laser power. Dot marks are the data recorded by optical measurements, the dashed line is the fit to extrapolate the temperature at the maximum power laser, (right) Picture of the cathode held at 1600°C .

Experiment	Cathode / Emitting layer	Anode
case A	8 nm-thick LaB-O ($\Phi_C = 3.26$ - 3.34 eV from UPS)	Gold (Au) anode ($\Phi_A = 5.0$ - 5.1 eV from UPS)
case B	15-nm-thick CeB-O emitting layer ($\Phi_C = 3.6$ - 3.9 eV from UPS)	p-type GaAs wafer / 40-nm-thick BaF2 coating anode ($\Phi_A = 3.7$ eV from UPS)
case C	15-nm-thick CeB-O emitting layer ($\Phi_C = 3.6$ - 3.9 eV from UPS)	n-type GaAs wafer / 40 nm-thick BaF2 coating anode ($\Phi_A = 3.8$ - 3.9 eV from UPS)

Table 7. Preliminary experimental configurations tested in the upgraded VTEC setup.

Figure 30: I(V) characteristics at the cathode temperature of 1260 ± 10 °C for the three configurations reported in Table 7.

The doping type of the GaAs anode (cases B and C) was changed to verify if a lower work function semiconductor (3.7 ± 0.2 eV for the n-type, 4.7 ± 0.1 eV for the p-type measured by UPS) is a more effective collector of electrons also when coated by BaF_2 . Contrarily from what found on bare doped GaAs wafers, **the work function of coated n-type and p-type seems to be very similar. This suggests that thermionic emission is not influenced by the substrate**, but it mainly depends on the surface properties of BaF_2 . This might be influenced by the BaF_2 thick layer (40 nm) which is deposited in these particular anodes. This large thickness probably introduces large ohmic losses in both **cases B and C**. Both configurations were tested and compared with the thermionic case (**case A**) tackled in the previous pages. Figure 30 shows the I(V) characteristics provided by the different cases at a fixed cathode temperature of 1260 ± 10 °C. For case B and C, the V_{oc} is higher than case of the classic thermionic case and ranges from 0.3 to 1.45 V. Besides, case B shows higher thermionic current densities at the same temperature if compared to case C, although the emitting layer was the same. This is probably due to a modification of the properties of the cathode surface (further inspection by XRD, XPS, and UPS is currently ongoing). Other possible explanations are i) a variation of the inter-electrode distance due to different thermal expansion mechanisms; and ii) a variation of the anode surface temperature.

Figure 31. New characterization setup for the measurement of the TPV conversion efficiency.

Figure 32: Preliminary efficiency measurement of a GaSb Commercial TPV cell (JX Crystals). The decrease in the efficiency in this case at high heat values is probably attributed to the heating of the TPV cell, which cannot be kept constant as a function of heat flux in the current setup.

Concerning the independent characterization of the TPV cells, UPM has developed a new characterization setup for measuring the TPV conversion efficiency (Figure 31). This measurement differentiates from “conventional” solar-PV measurement setups because in this case, net radiative transfer (incident minus reflected) must be considered to calculate the efficiency instead of simply considering the incident radiative power. This setup calculates the energy balance in the TPV cell by using a heat flux

sensor (gSKIN[®] XP: highly sensitive seebeck sensor from greenTEG) for measuring the dissipated heat (Q). Electric power is measured by conventional Keithley source-meter device. The TPV cell temperature is controlled by means of a high power Peltier cooler. Preliminary experiments (Figure 32) have been conducted on commercial GaSb TPV cells (from JX Crystals). Although promising results are already obtained, a fine tuning of the setup is still needed. In particular, it is needed to increase the radiative power in order to test the cells under larger power conditions, where they are expected to provide larger efficiencies.

Task 3.6: Fabrication of Final Devices and Proof of Concept Experiment

Not presently active.

Progress in WP4: Final Proof of Concept Experiment

This workpackage targets objective O4 (Demonstrate the proof of concept of the novel energy storage concept). Although this WP starts at the end of second year, some activities have been started in order to anticipate the discussion among partners about the best design for the final proof of concept experiment. In this regard, two kinds of geometries (inverted truncated pyramid -ITP- and hollow cylindrical -HC-, see Figure 33) have been evaluated theoretically using both quasi-1D analytical model (UPM) and CFD simulations (CERTH) (see Task 2.3). For the moment, both models assumed adiabatic container walls. This work is summarized in reference [8], and the main conclusions are:

- The higher discharge efficiency is obtained for devices where the cross-sectional area diminishes in the direction of heat flow. This results in highly tapered container for the ITP, and very small diameter for the inner cylinder in the HC case. This conclusion must be reassessed for the case of non-adiabatic walls, that will probably relax this condition. This assessment is being carried out in Task 2.3 by CERTH in collaboration with USTUTT.
- The thickness of PCM in the direction of heat flow must be minimized to avoid large temperature gradients from liquid PCM and the emitter. This brings a trade-off between storage capacity and conversion efficiency.

Taking into account the previous conclusions, the optimal geometries are shown in Figure 34, showing that completely different aspect ratios are needed in each of the configurations: In the ITP (HC) system the highest efficiency requires high (low) aspect ratios, i.e. low and wide (high and narrow) designs. Therefore, the final geometrical choice depends on practical concerns such as preferred aspect ratio, maximum allowable length of the container, minimum size of the TPV cell, etc.

In the particular case of AMADEUS project, ITP (or alternatively, an inverted conical design) will be targeted, the main reason being the simpler constructive design, and the simplicity of developing small prototypes (few 100's of ml) in this configuration.

Figure 33. Two geometries under consideration to fabricate the final proof of concept experiment: (left) Inverted Truncated Pyramid (ITP), and (right) Hollow-Cylindrical (HC).

Figure 34. Optimal geometrical configurations for both HC and ITP geometries

Conclusions

This report has described the main activities of the AMADEUS project during the first year of development. The project is progressing as expected, and all deliverables and milestones have been completed on time. Under WP2 (Energy Storage Block) a number of Si-B alloys and refractories have been characterized by different techniques at very high temperatures (up to 1750°C). Also, CFD simulation of the heat transfer within the heat storage block, including PCM and thermal insulation cover, has been conducted. Under WP3 (Energy Conversion Block), the separate elements of the converter (emitter, anode coating, TPV cell, and micro-spacers) have been already developed. Despite some optimizations are still needed, especially concerning the reduction of the anode work function, most of the elements required for starting the TIPV experiments are already available. A new VTEC setup has been developed and has been already used to characterize thermionic devices under UHV and high temperature (1250°C) conditions. This setup is ready to incorporate TIPV converters. Finally, under WP4 (Final Proof of Concept Experiment) some preliminary simulations have been conducted to identify the optimal geometrical configuration, to anticipate the discussion about the final experimental prototype.

List of Technical Publications

All the publications generated by the AMADEUS project are available at the AMADEUS Community at ZENODO: "Next Generation Materials and Solid State Devices for Ultra High Temperature Energy Storage and Conversion":

<https://zenodo.org/communities/amadeus-737054/?page=1&size=20>

I. Publications in journals and conference proceedings:

- [1]. W. Polkowski, N. Sobczak, R. Nowak, A. Kudyba, G. Bruzda, A. Polkowska, M. Homa, P. Turalska, O. Shuleshova, I. Kaban, Wetting behavior of Si-13.5B alloy on polycrystalline h-BN-based substrates, Transaction of Foundry Research Institute 57 (2017) 321-326, DOI: 10.7356/ioid.2017.32 (Open Access)
- [2]. A. Polkowska, M. Warmuzek, J. Kalarus, W. Polkowski, N. Sobczak, Scanning electron microscopy evaluation of selected Si/refractory sessile drop couples after wettability tests at ultra-high temperatures, Transaction of Foundry Research Institute 57 (2017), 337-344, DOI: 10.7356/ioid.2017.35 (Open Access)
- [3]. W. Polkowski, N. Sobczak, R. Nowak, A. Kudyba, G. Bruzda, A. Polkowska, M. Homa, P. Turalska, M. Tangstad, J. Safarian, E. Moosavi-Khoonsari, A. Datas, Wetting behavior and reactivity of molten silicon with h-BN substrate at ultrahigh temperatures up to 1750°C, Article accepted for publication in Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance 27(6), 2018 (Open Access) DOI: 10.1007/s11665-017-3114-8
- [4]. Lang, S.; Bestenlehner, D.; Marx, R.; Drück, H: Analysis of Mathematical Heat Transfer Models for free-flowing Vacuum Insulation Materials, Article Published online at <http://ivisparis2017.org> (Open Access)
- [5]. Lang, S.; Bestenlehner, D.; Marx, R.; Drück, H: Thermal Insulation of an Ultra-High Temperature Thermal Energy Store for Concentrated Solar Power, Article submitted to AIP Conference Proceedings (Open Access)
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- [7]. A. Datas, M. Zeneli, C. del Cañizo, I. Malgarinos, A. Nikolopoulos, N. Nikolopoulos, S. Karellas, A. Martí, Molten Silicon Storage of Concentrated Solar Power with Integrated Thermophotovoltaic Energy Conversion, SolarPaces 2017, Santiago, Chile., 2017. Article submitted to AIP Conference Proceedings (Open Access)

II. Presentations and posters on conferences, seminars, congresses:

- [8]. A.Datas, AMADEUS project: ultra high temperature energy storage and conversion, Seminar CIC Energigune, Vitoria - Gasteiz, 2017.
- [9]. A.Datas, AMADEUS project: ultra high temperature energy storage and conversion, Seminar at Helmholtz - Zentrum Dresden - Rossendorf, Institut für Fluidodynamik, Dresden, Germany, 2017.
- [10]. S. Lang, D. Bestenlehner, R. Marx, H. Drück, Analysis of Mathematical Heat Transfer Models for free-flowing Vacuum Insulation Materials, IVIS 2017 – 13th International Vacuum Insulation Symposium, <http://www.ivisparis2017.org/index.php?page=abstract-submission>, Paris, France, 2017, pp. 113-114.
- [11]. A. Polkowska, M. Warmuzek, J. Kalarus, W. Polkowski, N. Sobczak, A comparison of various imaging modes in scanning electron microscopy during evaluation of selected Si/refractory sessile drop couples after wettability tests at ultra-high temperature, 1st International Conference on Metals, Ceramics and Composites, Varna, Bulgaria, 2017.
- [12]. A. Grorud, Interaction of liquid Si-B alloys with graphite crucibles, NTNU Student Summerjob Seminar (???), date??.
- [13]. N. Sobczak, Invited lecture: Factors affecting wetting and reactivity in Si/ceramic systems at ultrahigh temperatures $T > 1450^\circ$, EUROMAT 2017, Thessaloniki, Greece, 2017.
- [14]. N. Sobczak, Invited lecture: Overview on high temperature interaction between liquid metals and ceramics: methodological, scientific and practical aspects, 8th Freiberg Refractory Forum, Freiberg, Germany, 2017.
- [15]. W. Polkowski, N. Sobczak, Oral: Dobór materiałów ogniotrwałych w wysokotemperaturowych systemach cieplnego magazynowania i konwersji energii - Refractory materials for Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage devices (in Polish), 2nd Scientific Conference on Foundrymen's Day, Cracow, Poland, 2017.
- [16]. B. Grorud, Oral: Interaction of liquid Si-B alloys with graphite crucibles, International student seminar (THS Armada Career), Stockholm, 2017.
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- [18]. S. Lang, D. Bestenlehner, R. Marx, H. Drück, Poster: Analysis of Mathematical Heat Transfer Models for free-flowing Vacuum Insulation Materials, IVIS 2017 – 13th International Vacuum Insulation Symposium, Paris, France, 2017.
- [19]. W. Polkowski, N. Sobczak, R. Nowak, A. Kudyba, G. Bruzda, A. Polkowska, M. Homa, P. Turalska, Poster: Effect of h-BN spray coatings on wetting and reactivity in Si/SiC system, 1st International Conference on Metals, Ceramics and Composites, Varna, Bulgaria, 2017.
- [20]. A. Polkowska, M. Warmuzek, J. Kalarus, W. Polkowski, N. Sobczak, Poster: Scanning electron microscopy evaluation of selected Si/refractory sessile drop couples after wettability tests at ultra-high temperatures, 1st International Conference on Metals, Ceramics and Composites, Varna, Bulgaria, 2017.

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List of Communication Actions (selection)

1. Amadeus & 1414 Degrees Energy Storage. Blog Deep resource. 21st August 2017. <https://deepresource.wordpress.com/2017/08/21/amadeus-1414-degrees-energy-storage/>
2. Silicon might be game-changer for energy storage. 11th September 2017. <https://smartcitynews.global/silicon-might-be-gamechanger-for-energy-storage/>
3. Will CSP Plants Operate at 2000°C by 2019 with New Silicon-based TES System? 24th August 2017. <http://en.cspplaza.com/2000%E2%84%83-by-2019%E2%81concentrated-solar-power-scientists-aiming-to-increase-operating-temperatures.html>
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6. International Seminar on Materials Science Frontiers. Introduction to AMADEUS research. Video available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2nyw-xV9u9c>
7. Solar news 69 2017. Industrial Spanish Journal devoted to Solar Energy
8. Energias Renovables, 158, Feb. 217. Industrial Spanish Journal devoted to Renewable Energy.
9. Future Energy Web <http://futureenergyweb.es/tag/almacenamiento-energetico/> 15/02/2017

10. Renewable Energy World.
<http://www.renewableenergyworld.com/articles/2017/02/europe-to-lead-research-project-for-energy-storage-in-molten-silicon.html> 20/02/2017
11. Mother Nature. 21/04/2017 <https://mothernature.com/2017/04/europe-to-lead-research-project-for-energy-storage-in-molten-silicon/>
12. Energy News. 24/02/2017 <http://www.energynews.es/english/the-upm-coordinates-first-european-project-to-store-energy-in-molten-silicon-exceeding-1000-c/>
13. ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/project/AMADEUS-Next-GenerAtion-MateriAls-and-Solid-State-DevicEs-for-Ultra-High-Temperature-Energy-Storage-and-Conversion>
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Disclaimer

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